

1 **Amyloid species are produced in induced pluripotent stem cells from humans with Alzheimer's**
2 **Disease.**

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7 We used human induced pluripotent stem cells, either mutant and wildtype isogenic *PSEN1* or CRISPR
8 edited to contain a mutation in *APOE* to understand if engineered mutation was sufficient to result in
9 transcriptional hallmarks of disease. We observed production of amyloid species early in disease in
10 human iPS cultures - both derived from cells of patients with disease and in cells engineered to contain
11 AD mutation. The data demonstrate that the identified AD mutations are likely causative, and confirm that
12 disease associated with or resulting from amyloid production and accumulation occurs early in disease
13 and a transcriptional correlate of it can be observed and measured within days.

Results

We measured total transcription in two induced pluripotent stem cell culture systems *in vitro* to address difficulties in studying Alzheimer's Disease biology late in disease *in vivo*: a culture system in which cortical neurons cultured for 80 days were derived from induced pluripotent stem cells engineered by CRISPR to contain a mutation in PSEN1 found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease, and a second induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPS) culture system in which neurons were derived from hiPS engineered to contain a variant of apolipoprotein E gene, APOE4, comparing total transcription to isogenic iPS containing APOE3.

Induction of amyloid beta precursor protein in cortical neurons derived from induced pluripotent stem cells

GSE128343

Figure 1: Amyloid beta precursor protein is produced in induced pluripotent stem cells containing the PSEN1 M164V mutation found in patients with early-onset Alzheimer's Disease.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
351	7.31e-46	0.0359	-14.2158494	-0.5106425	14938.72	APP	308/19352	98.4

Engineered PSEN1 M164V mutation was sufficient to induce production of APP in cortical neurons derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPS) in culture (Figure 1). The data clearly demonstrate that a mutation found in patients with early-onset Alzheimer's Disease is sufficient to result in biologically significant levels of amyloid beta precursor protein production. We next examined a second culture system in which neurons derived from hiPS were engineered to contain a variant in the apolipoprotein E (APOE) gene, APOE4, comparing total transcription by RNA-sequencing to an isogenic hiPS line containing APOE3.

Production of amyloid beta precursor protein in neurons derived from induced pluripotent stem cells engineered to express the APOE4 polymorphism found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease.

Figure 2: Amyloid beta precursor protein is produced in induced pluripotent stem cells containing the APOE4 variant found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease.

GSE203019

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
351	4.41E-05	0.1209	-4.08	-4.94E-01	3217.57	APP	3068/16827	81.7

Discussion

We presented here evidence that two separate mutations found in humans with Alzheimer's Disease are sufficient to result in high-level expression of a gene (*APP*) whose expressed product forms fibrils in the brains of humans with AD, amyloid beta.

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Methods

We used RNA-sequencing (GSE102596 and GSE128343) to measure total transcription in neuronal cell types derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells that had been engineered to contain mutations found in patients with Alzheimer’s Disease.